

OPNET: A NEW PARADIGM FOR SIMULATION OF ADVANCED COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

Jyoti Sekhar Banerjee¹
Debonita Goswami²
Shovon Nandi³

ABSTRACT

Various simulation tools play very important role in today's engineering & technological projects and in research works also. Using these tools researchers can realize, estimate & evaluate the performance of any system which is hard to implement in real time. In this paper, we have employed OPNET as a simulating tool to study different aspects of Wired and Wireless Communication technology. This work helps to create a prototype of any practical Networking project and evaluate the parameters of the communicating devices so that the Quality of Service (QoS) of the network is maintained. Consequently practical job becomes efficient, cost effective, unstrained and clean when the various parameters obtained from the simulation are actually used in the real time projects. Since it is impossible to do justice to this large body of research in this short survey, we discuss from a wide spectrum and level of work, such as. Since it is a large spectrum of research, we have confined ourselves to study how delay, load, Page Response Time, etc parameters vary from node to node in different environments, in this paper.

KEYWORDS: OPNET, Simulation, Networks, Ethernet, LAN, MAN, HUB, SWITCH.

INTRODUCTION

Network simulation is undoubtedly one of the most predominant evaluation methodologies in the area of computer networks. Hence practical insight in modern networking is a must for every network engineer in order to get a practical touch with reality in communication and networking whether it's wired or wireless. Due to their usefulness and power in providing the ability to quickly experiment with multiple design options in the design space, several simulators like REAL, NetSim, Harvard Simulator, NS-2, OMNeT++ etc have been designed by the academic community students and researchers today. In this very paper we have chosen OPNET (Optimized Network Engineering Tool) as a simulator and presented a detailed discussion of its features and use. We have also tried to summarize the relevant features which are of particular interest to different user-groups. Firstly we'll illustrate how OPNET can be used as a real life research tool to enhance the skill of network engineers. Another important contribution of this paper is the analytical modeling and simulation of some projects which are considered as an important part in an advanced course on telecommunication networks. The aim of the analytical modeling is to perform some simple calculations of some parameters (such as Delay) on a simplified network configuration which will serve as the performance of the network. To do so first, we have to create a representative topology and add the desired traffic on it; this resulted in existing traffic being defined as background traffic and the traffic from the new services being implemented as explicit traffic. From the simulation we obtain the result in graphical format using individual statistics.

OPNET As a Research Tool

¹ Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Bengal Institute of Technology, Kolkata-700150, India

² Tata Consultancy Services Ltd., India

³ Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Bengal Institute of Technology, Kolkata-700150, India

For addressing the high computation demands of recent state-of-art application domains, researchers need to employ efficient hardware platforms, versatile techniques and simulators etc. Here as a simulator, OPNET is found to be very useful because of its ability to simulate a wide spectrum of networking technologies. It also enables modeling the entire network, including its routers, switches, protocols, servers, and the individual applications they support. As a communications oriented simulation language, OPNET has the feature of providing direct access to the source code and an easy-to-use front end. OPNET models are composed of three primary model layers, namely, the process layer, the node layer and the network layer. The ability to build process models using finite state machines encourages a modular approach, since the complex networks can be broken down into individual states and further, each state can be individually defined and implemented. At the next level of abstraction node models are used which could be a predefined OPNET artifact or defined by user. Above this in the hierarchy lies the network model, which may represent a hierarchy of sub-networks. The experiences with laboratory and classroom projects using OPNET have found the tool as a great help in enhancing student learning and bringing student interest in computer network courses as it is used to help the students and researchers critically analyze, evaluate and explain the behavior and operation of contemporary data communication systems at an advanced level. Moreover, the researchers also get the opportunity to explore the facilities provided by the simulation tool to study the interoperability and performance issues relating to homogeneous and heterogeneous data communications environments and to design, simulate and evaluate appropriate networking solutions to a range of real life data communication problems. This low-cost environment for active learning fosters a better understanding among the students and researchers of the network through modeling and experimentation. Consequently the researchers get valuable hands-on experiences that let them think in terms of practical applications i.e. the guidelines to choose the best among the various possible design options in reality. Today, the applications of communications and networking systems are wide-spread, like- military, health, education etc and here OPNET is used as a powerful and flexible tool and obviously the choice of industry. Thus, due to its efficiency and detailed modeling, OPNET can prove to be a useful tool for researchers.

Features of OPNET

Generally OPNET is able to perform three main functions such as modeling, simulating and analysis. It provides very simple but comprehensive graphical environment for modeling i.e. to create all kind of models of protocols. Further for the simulation it uses three different but advanced simulations technologies and also can be used to address a wide range of studies. For analysis, the displayed data from simulation results can be analyzed very easily. The accessibility to the simulator development environment is very easy cause of its user friendly graphs, charts; statistics as well as the animations can be generated by OPNET. Simply OPNET is very convenient for its users and it has proven itself an essential tool for system design. And modeling with OPNET means that the users can confidently deliver design specifications that save time and money right from the beginning of the design lifecycle. Further few features of OPNET are enlisted below:

- Source code provide lots of components with its library
- Fast and discrete event simulation engine
- Modeling based on objects (Object Oriented Modeling)
- Graphical user interface supports 32-bit and 64-bit
- 32-bit and 64-bit parallel simulation kernel
- Graded or ordered modeling environment
- Wireless modeling is also customizable
- Scalable wireless simulation support
- Also support grid computing
- Hybrid, discrete event and analytical simulation

- Open interface for integrating external component libraries
- Comprehensive development environment
- GUI-based debugging
- Both behavior and performance of modeled systems can be analyzed by performing discrete event simulation
- Its object oriented approach with well-defined interfaces; (the changes made in one module minimally affect the other nodes or their functionality. Thus, merely by keeping an appropriate interface, the whole model works fine, as before.

So in brief it can be said that, OPNET is a versatile tool in the era of networking as it provides graphical editors to the users to edit his own devices, configure his own networks, design his own protocols, define his own packet formats, etc.

Simulation using OPNET

In this paper we have simulated some basic models of networking and evaluated its parameters like Delay, Load, Page Response Time etc. We will show here the OPNET models and the resultant graphs, the conclusion made from that result and verifying that with the real time scenario.

Analyzing the Performance of a 10BaseT Ethernet

A 10Base T network uses a physical star topology. In this paper, we will setup a 5-node 10BaseT network with an Ethernet hub at the center.

There is an Ethernet server connected to the hub and it provides the file transfer, web access, email services, etc. The 5 machines in the network will try to access the server for specific services. All the links are of 10Mbps bandwidth. Configuring the application profiles the simulation will be run for some time. Load, Collision count, utilization, and delay will be evaluated from result.

Figure 2: The Global Delay and the server's Load respectively

Figure 3: The Collision Count and Utilization of server

Comparing the Performance of Hubs and Switches in MAN

In this paper, we will compare the performance of hubs and switches in a medium scale LAN. The Sub network has about 120 machines and each runs web profiles connecting to a web server

Fig 4: Four sub networks connected by switch

Fig 5: Four sub networks connected by hub

In each subnet, we will have 15 machines hooked up exclusively to a hierarchy of hubs and both hubs connected to a bridge. The subnets are hooked up by a hub in one scenario while in another we have a switch being used.

Figure 5: Arrangement of machines in one sub network

Configuring the application profiles the simulation will be run for some time. Page response time will be evaluated from result. We can see well the page response time of any node of a sub network connected by switch is more than the sub network connected by hub.

Figure 6: the Page Response time of nodes of subnets connected by hub and switch

Analyzing the Performance of a Wireless LAN for Fixed Nodes

In this paper we have studied the performance of a wireless LAN and the effect of changing the number of nodes and the medium bandwidth. We will follow the IEEE 802.11 Medium-access protocol. We are going to play with data rate of 2 Mbps and the number of wireless stations in LAN varying from 5 to 7.

Figure 7: The WLAN arrangement with 5 nodes

Figure 8: The WLAN arrangement with 6 nodes

Figure 9: The WLAN arrangement with 7 nodes

Configuring the application profiles the simulation will be run for configurable amount of time. In graphs we can see the result that how delays is increasing with the increasing number of nodes.

Figure 10: The Delay of WLAN arrangement having 5,6 and 7 nodes

Analyzing the Performance of a Wireless LAN for Mobile Nodes

In this paper we have used wireless LAN mobile nodes same as the fixed nodes. We have kept two nodes in a position which are equidistance from the 1st node. We will follow the IEEE 802.11 Medium-access protocol. We are going to play with data rate of 2 Mbps.

Figure 11: The arrangement of WLAN mobile nodes

Configuring the application profiles the simulation will be run for some time. In graphs we can see the result. If we take mobile_node 0 as the pivot position then the comparative delay of mobile_node 1 is less than the comparative delay of mobile_node 2. Though the nodes are equidistance, the delays are unequal.

Figure 12: The media access delay of three WLAN mobile nodes

OPNET: COMPARISON WITH OTHER NETWORK SIMULATORS

As we know network simulator allows the researchers to test the scenarios that are difficult or expensive to simulate in real world. It is particularly useful to test new networking protocols or to change the existing protocols in a controlled and reproducible environment. One can design different network topologies using various types of nodes (hosts, hubs, bridges, routers and mobile units etc.) The network simulators are of different types which can be compared on the basis of: range (from the very simple to the very complex), specifying the nodes and the links between those nodes and the traffic between the nodes, specifying everything about the protocols used to handle traffic in a network, graphical applications (allow users to easily visualize the workings of their simulated environment.), text-based applications (permit more advanced forms of customization) and programming-oriented tools (providing a programming framework that customizes to create an application that simulates the networking environment to be tested.)

Now a days there are different network simulators with different features are available in the market. Some of them are OPNET, NS2, NS3, NetSim, OMNeT++, REAL, J-Sim, QualNet, etc.

NS2 (Network Simulator version 2): NS2 is a discrete event simulator targeted at networking research. It provides support for simulation of TCP, routing, and multicast protocols over all networks (wired and wireless). It uses C++ and Otcl software languages. C++ is fast to run but slower to change, making it suitable for detailed protocol implementation. Whereas Otcl runs much slower but can be changed very quickly (and interactively), making it ideal for simulation configuration. Ns provides glue to make objects and variables appear on both languages.

NS3 (Network Simulator version 3): NS3 is also an open sourced discrete-event network simulator which targets primarily for research and educational use. NS3 is licensed under the GNU GPLv2 license, and is available for research and development. It uses C++ and Python software languages. NS3 is built as a library which may be statically or dynamically linked to a C++ main program. These libraries define the start of simulation and simulation topology. C++ wrapped by Python and Python programs import an “ns3” module.

OPNET (Optimized Network Engineering Tools): It is extensive and powerful simulation software with wide variety of possibilities to simulate entire heterogeneous networks with various protocols. The main programming language in OPNET is C (recent releases support C++ development). The initial configuration (topology setup, parameter setting) is usually achieved using Graphical User Interface (GUI), a set of XML files or through C library calls. Simulation scenarios (e.g., parameter change after some time, topology update, etc.) usually require writing C or C++ code.

NETSIM (Network Based Environment for Modelling and Simulation): It is an application that simulates Cisco Systems networking hardware and software and is designed to aid the user in learning the Cisco IOS command structure. It uses Java language. It creates fast, platform independent software that could be used in simple, consumer electronic products. Java designed for simple, efficient, platform-independent program for creating WWW-based programs. Using Java one can create small programs called applets that are embedded into an HTML document and viewable on any Java-compatible browser. Java applets are compiled into a set of byte-codes, or machine-independent processing instructions.

OMNET++ (Optical Micro-Networks Plus Plus): It is an extensible, modular, component-based C++ simulation library and framework, primarily for building network simulators.

JSIM (Java-based simulation): It is a Java-based simulation system for building quantitative numeric models and analyzing them with respect to experimental reference data. JSim is an application development environment based on the component-based software architecture. Java is easy to learn and easy to use. In case of any problems, source texts provided with J-Sim can be used to generate new code, compiled in the target environment. JSim provides basic classes for simulation, process and queue. These classes can be either directly used or extended according to specific user's requirements.

QUALNET: It is a commercial version of GloMoSim used by Scalable Network Technologies for their defence projects. For implementing new protocols, QUALNET uses C/C++ and follows a procedural paradigm. It uses the parallel simulation environment for complex systems for basic operations, hence can run on distributed machines.

REAL (Realistic and Large): It is a network simulator originally for studying the dynamic behaviour of flow and congestion control schemes in packet-switched data networks. It provides users with a way of specifying such networks and to simulate their behaviours. The actions are C code that creates the graph structure. The combination of a workload and flow control protocol is implemented by a single C function. Each such function is executed in parallel by the underlying thread-based simulation package, and can be thought of as being an independently scheduled and non-preemptable entity.

Among these available Network simulators, NS2 and OPNET are acknowledged as most popular and useful in terms of performance. Both these general commercial simulators are called hybrid simulators, since they combine both methodologies to provide a reasonable speed and, at the same time maintaining accuracy in the critical areas. The simulation speed of both the simulators is high and thus they are quite fast. Compared to Ns-2, OPNET provides more diverse statistics modules at different levels, although this also adds to the overhead of the software. Ns-2, being a freeware is likely to be a choice of many students while as OPNET, due to the requirement of a license, would not be the as attractive. However, OPNET has a well-engineered GUI suitable for a commercial product, while as Ns-2 models require acquaintance with the tcl scripting language.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents the latest state-of-the-art technology on real-time simulation of modern wired & wireless communication systems. We have presented an exhaustive review, analysis and implementation details of OPNET from designing very basic model to simulate complex networks. OPNET Modeler and IT Guru are powerful tools that researchers can use during network modeling. OPNET software can offer researchers a broader insight in networking technologies, simulation techniques and the impact of applications on network performance. The advantages of our work are various, as we have presented some real time scenario and practical simulation by OPNET in each occurrence. From this paper beginner to professionals, everyone can be benefited by getting an idea on the flexibility of the OPNET, shortcomings of this tool and the type of application area where OPNET could be used for simulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors deeply acknowledge the support from Department of ECE, Bengal Institute of Technology (A unit of Techno India Group). The authors also wish to express appreciation to Prof. D. Ray, Director, Bengal Institute of Technology for his continuous support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Opnet technologies, www.opnet.com
- [2] S. Mittal et al., "OPNET: An Integrated Design Paradigm for Simulations," IEEE International Conference on Digital Convergence, pp. 204-209, 2011.
- [3] Theunis, B. Van den Broeck, P. Leys, J. Potemans, E. Van Lil, A. Van de Capelle OPNET in Advanced Networking Education Proc. to the International Conference on Networking ICN'01, Colmar, France, pp. 790-802, 2001.
- [4] Chang, 1999. Network simulations with OPNET. In Proceedings of the 31st Conference on Winter Simulation: Simulation—A Bridge To the Future – Vol.1 (Phoenix, Arizona, United States, December 05 - 08, 1999).
- [5] V.Y. Hnatyshin, and A.F. Lobo, 2008. Undergraduate data communications and networking projects using opnet and wireshark software. In Proceedings of the 39th SIGCSE Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (Portland, OR, USA. SIGCSE '08. ACM, New York, NY, pp. 241-245, March 2008.
- [6] Guo, W. Xiang, S. Wang, "Reinforce Networking Theory with OPNET Simulation", Journal of Information Technology Education, vol. 6, pp. 215-226, 2007.
- [7] Computing Curriculum. (2001). IEEE/ACM CC-2001 Task Force. <http://www.acm.org/sigcse/cc2001/index.html>
- [8] Comer, Hands-on networking with internet technologies (2nd ed.). Prentice Hall, 2004.
- [9] http://www.lmu.ac.uk/ies/comp/esp_lmu.html